

Does the Physicality of $(0, m_0 c^2) \rightarrow (p, E)$ Imply Physicality of $(x, ct) \rightarrow (x', t')$?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 2, 2024

In Newtonian mechanics there is a focus on a particle at rest being accelerated so that it has an energy (including motion effects) and a momentum, but there is usually a single frame, clock and ruler. In special relativity, one may think of a rest frame and a frame moving with a constant v and consider $(0, m_0 c^2)$ and $(x=0, t)$ in the rest frame and (p, E) , (x', ct') in the moving using a Lorentz transformation to link the two.

The point we wish to make is that one may simply consider a rest frame and an mo accelerated to v . Then, like in Newtonian mechanics, the moving particle is considered to have a (p, E) even though in its rest frame it has m_0 . If one watches the particle move in the rest frame, then it seems that there is only the rest frame x, t . No physicality is usually assigned to x', t' . We suggest, however, that since $(0, m_0 c^2) \rightarrow (p, E)$ and both sets represent physicality, the fact that x', t' depend on v in the same manner as p, E , that there should be physicality as well linked x', t' . In other words, it is not enough to consider x, t as simply space-time co-ordinates. There is a v (and hence energy-momentum) sense of physicality to them. We argue that this physicality is the resolution \hbar/p and \hbar/E . Thus, we suggest that some physical attribute is to be expected.

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics, one usually considers a rest frame with a particle either at rest or moving in this frame which has a fixed clock and ruler. It is possible to perform a Galilean transformation, but the idea is that the ruler and clock represent a fixed reality of space-time and are not physical attributes of the particle linked to v .

Special Relativity

In classical mechanics, one follows a particle through $x(t)$, i.e. its trajectory. One does not consider a relationship with arbitrary x, t points - it is the trajectory $x-t$ values which are of interest. In establishing the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass, one has $(p=0, m_0 c^2)$ and $(x=0, t)$ in the rest frame and transforms to p, E and x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$. In this case, x', t' represent the trajectory of the particle. It is, however, possible to have many trajectories in the sense that one may change t and $x=0$ to $x=x_1$ etc. In other words, one may map various (x, t) in the rest frame to (x', t') in the moving and so one has a picture of all of $x'-t'$ space and not just a trajectory. This is expressed by the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et' + px' \quad ((1))$$

Any value of t', x' may be entered into ((1)) to obtain an A value. Thus, ((1)) is a statement about $x'-t'$ space and no longer simply about a trajectory.

Physicality of (pc,E)

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle may be at rest with m_0 . If work is done (a force applied), it may be accelerated so that it has momentum p and energy E . Thus, the particle has undergone a physical change which may be experimentally measured. A moving particle may collide with a target while one at rest does not. In other words, viewing a rest particle with m_0 from a frame moving with constant $-v$ is equivalent to creating a physical change in the particle to move it and then watching it in the rest frame.

The Lorentz transformation, however, changes $(0, m_0 c c)$ to (pc, E) and this represents a physical change. At the same time, the same Lorentz transformation changes (x,t) to (x',t') and we argue that this too should represent a physical change. In other words there should be physicality to x,t and x',t' and not just the view of an external ruler and clock.

In the above section, however, we argued that x',t' represents all of space-time and not just the trajectory of the particle. Thus, if there is physicality, it must somehow be linked with all of space-time. This begs the question: What is this physicality?

Physicality of x',t'

We suggest that the degeneracy of $A = -Et + px$, i.e.

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E, \quad n = \text{integer} \quad ((2))$$

Shows that there are degenerate points in space-time with the same A . These are dependent on the values of p, E which represent physical changes in the particle. We suggest that the resolutions suggested by \hbar/p and \hbar/E are also physical and represent the way in which the force interaction “changes”, so to speak, not only m_0 , but x, t as well. In other words, special relativity seems to dictate that there are physical changes in space-time when one accelerates a particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that since a Lorentz transformation acts on both $(p=0, m_0 c c)$ and (x, t) and that one consider m_0 changing to p, E to represent a physical change in these variables, then we suggest that there should actually be a physical change in x, t due to the force as well. We note that $A = -Et' + px'$, a Lorentz invariant, leads to degenerate A values for ((2)) so space-time overall is changed due to these resolutions in t and x ($\hbar/E, \hbar/p$). x', t' may be any value in A and so overall space-time is described, but one cannot simply think of this as an external ruler and clock. We argue that these are properties, like, m_0 becoming p, E physically, which are physically linked to the acceleration/force and must physical manifest the work done-energy supplied We thus suggest that one expects a physical manifestation based on v to be associated with the change from x, t to x', t' as space-time, like p, E , is a property of the particle which depends on the work done on it.